

QUALITY MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATION BASED ON FOREIGN EXPERIENCES

Sharipova Gulchehra Farxod qizi

Termez state university, Master's of Pedagogical faculty (second course)

shgulchehra@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The effectiveness of the quality assurance system for higher education has been shown at the international level. The relevance of the problem of quality assurance in the innovative space of higher education is considered, first of all, in the context of the global space of higher education. Reforms in the operational and strategic management of education led to the introduction of recommendations and standards for quality assurance in the ESG European Higher Education Area. The main factors of quality assurance in the innovative space of higher education and the main principles of reforming the European space of higher education are highlighted. An effective tool for ensuring the quality of higher education is academic integrity, which is recognized as the moral code and ethical rules of the educational, scientific, and civilized community. Based on the results of the project "Impact of Policies for Plagiarism in Higher Education Across Europe" in 27 EU member states, the systems and methods of combating plagiarism were analyzed and recommendations were made regarding the need to popularize the institutional culture of academic integrity.

Key words: *European Framework for Quality Management , Economist Intelligence , Europe, Middle East and Africa GATS: General Agreement on Trade in Services in higher education institution, International Standards Organisation Ministry of Education , Total Quality Management .*

Introduction. The major factors that affect education systems are the resources and money that are utilized to support those systems in different nations, as well as how education is organized and administered to students. As we might expect, a country's wealth has much to do with the amount of money spent on education. Ensuring quality in the innovative space of higher education for all citizens is the main thing for creating a fair and high-quality society dreamed of by mankind, which is a kind of signpost for the development of our civilization. Quality education changes a person, the surrounding reality, his worldview, and the future. The course of the historical civilizational development of the world with the improvement of the innovative space of higher education led to the transition to the information society from the industrial one. In such a society, information has the highest value, and the source of innovative information in developed countries of the world reaches 80% of national wealth. With this approach, the main task of state importance becomes the perspective of education in the country and ensuring the high quality of the educational space (Vasyliuk et al., 2019). Today, the educational community at the international level believes that there cannot and should not be a clearly defined international effective system of ensuring quality assurance for higher education. Each civilized country solves the issue of quality assurance in the innovative space of higher education, taking into account the peculiarities of the national education system.

Results and Discussion. We will consider the peculiarities of prioritization and actualization of the improvement of the quality assurance process in the innovative space of higher education, teaching in higher education in national cases.

Austria. According to the Federal Ministry of Science, Research and Economy in higher education in Austria, the task of improving teaching is determined by the following procedures and documents: 1. The National Universities Development Plan has been in effect since 2016, to improve the relevant indicators and quality of teaching in higher education regarding the learning outcomes of higher education applicants. 2. A component of the system of external quality assurance in the

innovative space of higher education is ensuring and improving the quality of teaching.

3. The educational process in Austrian universities is not regulated at the national level but belongs to the autonomy of universities. Therefore, the issue of ensuring the quality of higher education is reflected indirectly in the framework of the performance agreement, which is signed by the Ministry of Education, Science and Research and higher education institutions. According to this agreement, state universities are responsible for the quality of education and teaching.

Netherlands. At the national level, the document "The Value of Knowledge, Strategic Agenda for Higher Education and Research 2015-2025" is in force, which defines the main goals of the strategic development of higher education institutions: access to education, world-class higher education, development of young talents, diversity of teaching methods and social activity. The successful implementation of the quality assurance process in the innovative space of higher education depends on such strategic goals. The main mechanisms and tools of the process of ensuring the quality of higher education are digitalization of the educational process, professional development of teachers, etc. The Association of Universities of the Netherlands is coordinating the implementation of the paradigm of improving the quality of higher education in the country.

Ireland. In the country, attention is focused on improving learning and teaching in higher education:

1. In Ireland, the Strategic Innovation Fund (SIF) was created, which supports projects to improve learning and teaching in higher education (the early 2000s).
2. The National Forum for the Enhancement of Teaching and Learning was created in the country, which directs all the efforts of universities to the improvement of teaching and learning (it offers a road map for the digitalization of higher education, presents the National Framework for the professional development of academic staff of higher education institutions and offers several innovative initiatives (end 2012)).
3. The introduction of the National Learning Impact Awards promotes the recognition and wide sharing of best practices in higher education: teaching and learning.

Norway. In January 2017, the Ministry of Education and Research issued the document "Quality Culture in Higher Education", which spells out public expectations and defines tasks for improving the process of quality assurance in the innovative space of higher education, namely the government: 1. Demands from institutions of higher education: valuing the activities of teachers and raising their status, developing and supporting teaching initiatives, improving the quality assurance process in the innovative space of higher education, improving the quality of teaching; a fixed reward system for the best practicing teachers; at all stages of the academic career of promoting the professional development of teachers. 2. Expects from institutions of higher education successful expert evaluation, implementation of innovative practices, and collegial mentoring aimed at improving teaching to strengthen the culture of quality. 3. To improve the quality of higher education, it introduces a national electronic database; support for research, etc. (relevant national initiatives), which promotes trust and is generally aimed at improving the quality of higher education and the quality of learning and teaching in particular (Kalashnikova et al., 2023).

Conclusion: About two decades for the development of the European area of higher education are considered the basis for ensuring the quality of higher education based on ESG recommendations and European standards. In the European space, the adoption of ESG became the determining factor of changes in ensuring the quality of education. This approach provided the basis for the creation and introduction of a register of independent quality assurance agencies. The Bucharest Communiqué of 2012 allowed all agencies registered in EQAR (European Quality Assurance Register for Higher Education) to carry out their activities in the entire European space in compliance with national requirements. In the development of the quality of higher education, the main aspects are student-centered learning, the involvement of employers in the educational process, the expansion of groups of interested parties, the use of modern information and communication technologies in education, etc. (Kuharskyi et al., 2018). The first attempt to develop the concept of quality assurance in the innovative space of higher education belongs to the developers of the World

Declaration adopted in October 1998 at the initiative of UNESCO on higher education for the 21st century. Nowadays, all states that joined the European Higher Education Area direct their functions to the implementation of the process of quality assurance in the innovative area of higher education, in coordination between the governments of the European countries of structural reforms. In this document, quality assurance in the innovative space of higher education appeared as a multidimensional strategy that covers all its activities and functions: scientific research and scholarships, educational programs, education seekers, staffing, buildings, equipment, material and technical base, academic environment (Neave, 1998). Quality improvement was proposed to be achieved by taking into account the conditions and realities of the organization of the educational process, harmonizing the internal self-evaluation of higher education institutions with expert external evaluation, and involving interested parties in institutional evaluation.

GLOSSARY:

Management EFQM: European Framework for Quality Management

EIU: Economist Intelligence Unit EMEA: Europe, Middle East and Africa

GATS: General Agreement on Trade in Services

HE: higher education HEI (s): higher education institution(s)

ISO: International Standards Organisation

MOE: Ministry of Education

OECD: Organisation for Economic Development.

QFD: Quality Function Deployment Model

TQM: Total Quality Management.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullah, F. (2006) Measuring Service Quality in Higher Education: HEdPERF Versus SERVPERF.
2. Marketing Intelligence and Planning, 24(1), 31 – 47. Al-Turki, U. and Duffuaa, S. (2003)
3. Performance Measures for Academic Departments. International Journal of Educational Management, 17(7), 330 – 338.
4. Aly, N. and Akpovi, J. (2001) Total Quality Management in California Public Higher Education, Quality Assurance in Education, 9(3),127 -131.
5. Arif, M. and Smiley, F. (2004) Baldrige theory into practice: a working model, International Journal of Educational Management, 18(5), 324 – 328.
6. Avdjieva, M. & Wilson, M. (2002) Exploring the development of quality in higher education, Managing Service Quality, 12(6), 372 – 383.
7. Badri, M. and Abdulla, M. (2004) Awards of Excellence in Institutions of Higher Education: an AHP approach. International Journal of Educational Management, 18 (4), 224 – 242.
8. Baker, R. (2002) Evaluating Quality and Effectiveness: Regional Accreditation Principles and Practices, Journal of Academic Librarianship, 28(1), 3- 7.
9. Blackmur, D. (2004) Issues in Higher Education Quality Assurance. Australian Journal of Public Administration, 63(2), 105 – 116.
10. Borahan, N.G. & Ziarati, R. (2002) Developing Quality Criteria for Application in the Higher Education Sector in Turkey, Total Quality Management, 13(7), 913 – 926.
11. Becket, N. and Brookes, M. (2006) Evaluating Quality Management in University Departments, Quality Assurance in Education, 14(2), 123 – 142.
12. Burbules, N. and Torres, C. (2000) Globalisation and Education: Critical Perspectives, Routledge: New York. Calvo-Mora, A., Leal, A. and Roldan, J. (2006).
13. Using enablers of the EFQM model to manage institutions of higher education, Quality Assurance in Education, 14(2), 99-122. Carrington, R., Coelli, T. and Rao, D. (2005)